

A study of solvent dependence and proton transfer kinetics of 2,6-diphenylphenol

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Manuscript received 18 January 2000, accepted 20 April 2000

Absorption and fluorescence solvatochromic shifts of 2,6-diphenylphenol reveal the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding in a non-polar solvent and intermolecular hydrogen bonding in polar solvents. The stretched sigmoidal fluorimetric titration curves indicate that the rates of excited state proton transfer are comparable to the rates of deactivation of conjugate pair. These curves are analysed using life-times of the species. The excited state equilibrium constants determined from rate constants and by other methods are compared.

The effects of solvents and pH on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of hydroxy compounds of naphthalenes¹ and phenanthrene² have been studied. The fluorimetric titrations of these compounds give stretched sigmoidal curves with two inflection points. A similar study on hydroxybiphenyls³⁻⁵ has revealed interesting features. The electronic spectral behaviour of 2-hydroxybiphenyl is found to be different from 3- and 4-hydroxybiphenyls. A dual emission was observed for 2-hydroxybiphenyl in polar solvents⁴. IR spectral study of the compound revealed the formation of *cis* and *trans* isomers due to the interaction of OH group with the π -cloud of the unsubstituted phenyl ring⁶. This type of O-H--- π interaction was also reported for 2,6-diphenylphenol in CCl₄ solution⁷. This intramolecular interaction in non-polar solvents and intermolecular interaction in polar solvents have significant impact on the electronic spectra. Hence in the present work we investigated solvatochromic and prototropic studies on the spectral behaviour of 2,6-diphenylphenol (DPP).

Results and Discussion

Effect of solvents : The absorption and fluorescence spectra of DPP were recorded in different solvents and the relevant data are compiled along with spectral data for 2-hydroxybiphenyl (HBP) in Table 1. Analysis of absorption solvatochromic shifts shows that there is no significant shift with polarity of the solvents except water. A blue-shift is observed in water. Comparison of the fluorescence spectra of DPP in various solvents reveals that there is a continuous red-shift with increasing polarity and hydrogen bonding ability of solvents. But the red-shift is much less compared to HBP.

Table 1. Absorption maxima (nm), log ϵ and fluorescence maxima (nm) of 2,6-diphenylphenol and 2-hydroxybiphenyl in different solvents and at various acid concentrations

Solvent	2,6-Diphenylphenol			2-Hydroxybiphenyl ^a		
	λ_{abs}	log ϵ	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	log ϵ	λ_{flu}
Cyclohexane	294.2	3.78	347.0	244.0	3.88	322.0
	238.0	4.42		283.0	3.54	
Ether	293.8	3.85	354.2			
	237.2	4.48				
Dioxane	295.4	3.85	358.0			
	238.6	4.48				
Ethyl acetate	294.2	3.79	356.1			
	241.4	4.23				
Chloroform	294.0	3.79	356.1			
	243.0	4.38				
Dichloromethane	293.4	3.79	347.4			
	237.6	4.41				
<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	294.8	3.74	354.2			
	239.0	4.46				
Acetonitrile	294.8	3.81	352.8	245.0	4.08	330.0
	238.2	4.47		286.8	3.71	396.6
Isopropyl alcohol	294.2	3.76	353.5			
	238.2	4.45				
Methanol	294.0	3.75	353.8	245.0	3.99	332.0
	237.0	4.43		286.5	3.63	398.0
Glycol	295.0	3.78	354.1			
	238.8	4.31				
Water	289.0	3.76	355.0	241.8	4.04	343.0
	233.0	4.47	436.0	281.4	3.68	415.0
Anion	326.5	-	436.0	343.0	-	415.0

^aFrom Ref. 4.

The absorption and fluorescence maxima are significantly red-shifted to HBP in cyclohexane. This large red-shift in a non-polar solvent may be due to intramolecular O-H--- π interaction of the molecule. In polar hydrogen bonding solvents the intermolecular solvent in-

teraction with OH group is predominant. The solvent interaction is much less in non-polar solvent and hence a red-shift in absorption and fluorescence is generally observed from non-polar to polar solvents. But in this case due to intramolecular O-H--- π interaction in non-polar solvent and intermolecular interaction in polar solvents, there is no significant solvatochromic shift in absorption. A small red-shift (8 nm) is observed in fluorescence from non-polar to polar solvent. The O-H--- π intramolecular interactions in non-polar media has already been reported in the IR spectral study of DPP

The very poor correlation of Stoke's shifts with the solvent polarity parameters $E_T(30)$ ⁸ and BK⁹ values (Table 2) is also due to the presence of different types of interactions in different solvents. The blue-shift observed in water is due to its hydrogen donor interaction with the DPP molecule.

Table 2. Stoke's shift (cm^{-1}) observed for DPP in different solvents with $E_T(30)$ and BK values

Solvent	$\Delta\nu_{\text{OH}}$	$E_T(30)^a$	BK ^b
Cyclohexane	5172	31.2	-0.001
Ether	5804	34.6	0.396
Dioxane	5919	36.0	0.043
Ethyl acetate	5908	38.1	-
Chloroform	5932	39.1	0.372
Dichloromethane	5298	41.1	0.586
<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	5689	43.9	0.673
Acetonitrile	5577	46.0	0.864
Isopropyl alcohol	5702	48.6	0.766
Methanol	5749	55.5	0.858
Glycol	5638	56.3	-
Water	6433	63.1	0.913
Correlation coefficient			
$E_T(30)$	0.4748		
BK	0.3334		

^aFrom Ref 8 ^bFrom Ref 9

Effect of acid concentration : The spectral characteristics of various prototropic equilibria in S_0 and S_1 states of the DPP molecule have been studied in the $H_0/pH/H_-$ range of -4 to 16. The absorption and fluorescence maxima of prototropic species are given in Table 1. The absorption and fluorescence spectra of DPP and DPP⁻ are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The absorption maxima of 289 and 233 nm at pH 7 are attributed to neutral form of DPP. When the pH is increased from 7, a red-shifted absorption spectrum with the maximum at 326.5 nm is obtained due to the formation of anion. The pK_a value for the equilibrium (1),

was calculated spectrophotometrically to be 9.95.

The fluorescence spectrum in water at pH 7 shows two maxima at 355 and 436 nm. In aqueous solution when pH

Fig. 1. The absorption spectra of different prototropic species of DPP

Fig. 2. The fluorescence spectra of different prototropic species of DPP < 1, only one band at 355 nm and when pH > 12, a single band at 436 nm is observed. This indicates that the maximum at 355 nm is due to the neutral form and that at 436 nm is attributed to anion. The excited state acidity constant (pK_a^*) for the equilibrium (1) was calculated using Förster cycle method¹⁰ (Table 3). These values clearly indicate that the molecule is a stronger acid in S_1 state than in S_0 state

Table 3. Ground and excited singlet state acidity constants of 2,6-diphenylphenol

Equilibrium	pK_a	pK_a^*	Förster cycle method			pK_a from rate constants
			pK_a^* (FT)	pK_a^* (flu)	pK_a^* (ave)	
			(abs)	(flu)	(ave)	pK_a (R)
Neutral $\rightleftharpoons$	9.95	0.6	1.60	-1.04	0.28	1.14
Anion						

The relative fluorescence intensities of the neutral (ϕ/ϕ_0) and anionic (ϕ'/ϕ'_0) forms for equilibrium (1) are plotted as a function of H_0/pH (Fig. 3). Examination of the fluorimetric titration curves indicates that these are stretched sigmoidal curves with two inflection points, one of which corresponds to pK_a (9.95) and the other to pK_a^* (0.6). There is a plateau region in pH range 2.0–7.5. The

Fig. 3. Plot of relative fluorescence intensities of the neutral (ϕ/ϕ') and anionic (ϕ_0/ϕ'_0) forms of DPP.

stretched sigmoidal curves indicate that the rate of proton transfer in S_1 state is comparable to the rates of fluorescence¹¹. The shapes of the fluorimetric titration curves can be explained on the basis of the kinetics of the excited state proton transfer reaction (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 explains the above behaviour where k_1 is the pseudo-first order rate constant for proton transfer from the excited molecule and k_f and k_i are the rate constants for fluorescence and radiationless deactivation of DPP. The primed values are the analogous terms of DPP^- . If the equations derived by Weller¹² using simple steady state kinetics are applied then the relative quantum yields of DPP (ϕ/ϕ_0) and DPP^- (ϕ'/ϕ'_0) are given by equations (3) and (4), where τ_0 and τ'_0 are the life-times of the DPP and DPP^- , respectively,

$$\phi/\phi_0 = \frac{1 + k'_1 \tau'_0 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]}{1 + k_1 \tau_0 + k'_1 \tau'_0 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi'/\phi'_0 = \frac{k_1 \tau_0}{1 + k_1 \tau_0 + k'_1 \tau'_0 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]} \quad (4)$$

If the rate of the reaction with solvent molecule in eqn. (2) is comparable with or greater than the rate of fluorescence of DPP and the rate of second order protonation of DPP^- is much less than the rate of fluorescence, eqns. (3) and (4) become

$$\phi/\phi_0 = \frac{1}{1 + k_1 \tau_0} \quad (5)$$

$$\phi'/\phi'_0 = \frac{k_1 \tau_0}{1 + k_1 \tau_0} \quad (6)$$

Since in equations (5) and (6), ϕ/ϕ_0 and ϕ'/ϕ'_0 are independent of $[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{OH}^-]$ flat regions are obtained for both the species. The values of ϕ/ϕ_0 and ϕ'/ϕ'_0 obtained from the flat regions are 0.23 and 0.84, respectively. In this case the sum of ϕ/ϕ_0 and ϕ'/ϕ'_0 is slightly greater than unity (1.07). If $\phi/\phi_0 + \phi'/\phi'_0 = 1$, proton transfer will occur before the deactivation of the excited state. This was observed in the case of 9-phenanthrol². In 3-hydroxybiphenyl⁵ the said sum is less than unity (0.61) and this decrease is reported due to the radiationless deactivation of the anion formed. However, like 4-hydroxybiphenyl ether¹³ and 2,2'-dihydroxybiphenyl¹⁴, in this case also, the sum of ϕ/ϕ_0 and ϕ'/ϕ'_0 is greater than unity and so the values of $k_1 \tau_0$ calculated from eqns. (5) and (6) are different.

The ratio of relative quantum yields is obtained by dividing eqn. (3) by (4),

$$\frac{\phi/\phi_0}{\phi'/\phi'_0} = \frac{1}{k_1 \tau_0} + \frac{k'_1 \tau'_0}{k_1 \tau_0} [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+] \quad (7)$$

In the range 0.1–0.32 M of $[\text{H}^+]$ (pH 0.5–1.0), $\phi/\phi_0 + \phi'/\phi'_0 = 1.0$. Hence in this range (ϕ/ϕ_0)/(ϕ'/ϕ'_0) values are plotted against $[\text{H}^+]$. This plot is linear with a good correlation ($r = 0.9982$). The values of $k_1 \tau_0$ and $k'_1 \tau'_0$ determined from the intercept and slope (least-square method) are 0.2382 and 3.638, respectively.

The life-times of DPP and DPP^- determined using a single-photon counting spectrofluorimeter are 0.201 and 0.244 ns, respectively. The rate constants k_1 and k'_1 are 1.185 and 16.24, respectively. The pK_a^* value calculated from the rate constants is 1.14. In the fluorimetric titration, the middle point of the inflection of the curves of the lower pH side is around 0.6, which is close to the pK_a^* (R) value of 1.14 obtained from the rate constants. The pK_a^* (R) value is the best value.

Experimental

DPP (Aldrich) was purified by recrystallisation from water. The purity of the compound was checked by noting its sharp m.p. and identical fluorescence spectra on excitation at different wavelengths. All the solvents used were of spectrograde or AnalR grade. Triple-distilled water was used. Analytical grade sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide were used as such. Solutions in the pH range 1.5–12 were prepared by adding appropriate amounts of NaOH and H_3PO_4 . A modified Hammett's acidity scale (H_0)¹⁵ for solutions below pH 1.5 (using H_2SO_4 - H_2O mixture) and Yagil's basicity scale (H_-)¹⁶ for solutions above pH 13 (using NaOH- H_2O mixture) were employed. Absorption

spectra were recorded on a Jasco UNIDEC-7800 spectrophotometer and fluorescence spectra on a Jasco FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. Fluorescence life-times were measured using picosecond, single-photon counting spectrometer Milenia (SW) CW 532 nm pumped Tsunami-Ti-sapphire mode locked laser with pico/femto option. pH was measured on an Elico LI IOT pH meter. The solutions were prepared just before taking the measurements. The concentrations of the solutions were of order of 10^{-4} – 10^{-5} M. The isosbestic wavelengths were used as excitation wavelengths for measuring the fluorescence intensities at any analytical wavelengths.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to National Centre for Ultra Fast Processes (NCUFP), Chennai, for providing facilities to measure life-times of the compound.

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